

**DEVELOPMENTAL AGE OF CHILDREN OF PRESCHOOL AGE AND
THE FORMATION OF INITIATIVE****Kadyrova Omadkhan Sobirjonovna**

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Abstract. The article gives important recommendations about the developmental age of children of preschool age, their specific characteristics, and the indispensable characteristics of an initiative person.

Key words: Pre-school age, pupil, upbringing, age-related characteristics, age periods, psychological characteristics, initiative, leader, quality, phenomenon.

Enter. Anatomical, physiological (physical) and psychological characteristics of children of preschool age, characteristic of a certain age period, are called age characteristics. Education and training work is organized taking into account these young characteristics. Then the influence of upbringing on the child's development will be strong. It is important to know and take into account the characteristics of different age periods in the child's development for the correct approach to children's upbringing and successful teaching. Because the growth and development of the child's organism, as well as mental development, are different at different ages. Abu Ali Ibn Sina, Jan Amos Comensky, K. D. Ushinsky, Abdullah Awlani also emphasized the need to educate a child. It is very difficult to take into account the unique characteristics of a child. Because children of the same age can be mentally different. For example, vision and hearing, activity, quick perception, slow thinking, impulsiveness or restraint, eloquence or lack of eloquence, enthusiasm or lack of enthusiasm, laziness or industriousness, clumsiness or indolence, compactness or lack of work. such as rapid onset are the effects of the nervous system, and the educator must know them.

Manifestation of individual initiative in society is one of the priority steps on the way to prosperity. This initiative is one of the important phenomena for the progress and development of the state. In today's era of globalization and information processes, individual initiative is gaining importance. The importance of individual initiative can be seen in the words of the President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev in the framework of "Five important initiatives" - "it would certainly be beneficial if every person felt the sense of initiative."

The main part. In order to know the individual characteristic of a child, it is important to know the general types of temperament and the methodology of studying the child's

characteristic. Temperament is a set of individual psychological characteristics of a person, which means "relationship of parts to each other" from the Latin "temperamentum". Also, there are specific laws of development of different age periods. The physical and mental maturity of a preschool child is conventionally divided into the following periods: Infancy (up to 1 year); Early age (1-2 years); First age group (2-3 years old); Young age (3-4 years); Middle age (4-5 years); Older age (5-6 years); School preparatory period (6-7 years old)

1. Peculiarities in the development of early childhood children. The period of human development begins in the mother's womb. During nine months in the mother's womb, the child goes through a very rapid development process and a period of complex development. During this period, the child is influenced by the external environment to a certain extent. Therefore, it is necessary to ensure that this effect is positive. If the weight of the baby at birth was 3.5 kg and the height was 50 cm, at three months its weight is about 5 kg, its height is 60 cm, and at the age of 6 months it is about 7 kg, height will be 64 cm. A child's development under the age of one year is mainly influenced by the family environment, and he should be fed with mother's milk. Even if the child does not have speech during this period, he has the ability to understand speech, understand, perceive actions, and recognize family members.

That is why the child's speech and thinking develop rapidly from infancy to the age of three. The child begins to speak the first words before the age of one year. During this period, adults, mainly family members, should take care of the baby properly. They should not be indifferent to the child saying that "he does not understand", they should correctly pronounce the names of objects in the environment and open a wide path for the correct development of their speech. When raising a child in a family, it is necessary to achieve closeness between the parents and the child. Parents should never leave education to their own devices, that is, it is necessary to start this process from an early age of the child. Because the child learns the first life experience in the family, observes and learns how to behave in different situations. Whatever we teach the child, it is necessary to strengthen it with concrete, real examples, that is, the child follows what the adults say, which ensures the effectiveness of personal education.

2. Developmental characteristics of the first age group (2-3 year old children). This period has its own characteristics. During the period from one to two years, the child's speech and the ability to understand the words spoken by others develop rapidly, and by the age of 2-3, the process of imitating the speech of others begins. The child is quickly influenced by music and artistic words. Therefore, it is necessary to teach him to recite poems and dance from the same period. They develop the skills of singing along with adults, moving in accordance with the

music, and feeling the melody. When children of this age are brought together, the skills of mutual communication begin to form among them. Educational activities should be directed to the development of the same skills that are beginning to form in children and turning them into skills.

3. Developmental characteristics of the small group (3-4 year old children). When a child reaches the age of 3, his physical growth slows down. During this period, its weight reaches 14-15 kg, its height reaches 90-95 cm. The child is physically fit and the nervous system is developing. Basic movement organs improve. 3-year-old children have the ability to control their behavior for a short period of time. Their independence increases, emotions and sensory perception develop. The skills of playing as a team are formed. The possibility of differentiating labor activities performed on the basis of the game will expand. The first manifestations of visual activity and building-making activity are shown. The attention of three-year-old children partially focuses, their memory is strengthened, the process of perception of material existence begins, and the possibilities of hypothesis arise. Gaming plays a leading role in this. This program is aimed at defining a system of educational training that paves the way for expansion and development of this activity.

4. Developmental characteristics of the middle group (4-5 year old children). When a child reaches the age of four, his physical growth accelerates somewhat, during this period his height grows to 105-108 cm, and his weight is 18-19 kg. During this period, the child's brain develops rapidly. The activity of the cortex of the large hemispheres is improving. Serious qualitative changes occur in the development of the child's basic movements, their naturalness increases, children develop the ability to compare. Children of this age speak fluently, have a deep memory, and the level of independent thinking is somewhat developed. He tries to perform all actions and activities independently. At this age, the child is extremely active, playful, and very curious. He willingly participates in any event. That is why it is important to feed them properly, put them to sleep on time, protect their health, monitor their mental state, and ensure that they are in a cheerful mood. It is expedient to direct the content of training with them to this.

5. Developmental characteristics of the older group (5-6 year old children). During this period, the height of the child grows by 7-8 cm. His legs develop faster than his body, his weight is 20-22 kg. Children's spines can become crooked because they have not hardened.

Therefore, it is necessary to pay special attention to ensure the proper growth of bones. Their heart is 4-5 times larger than a baby's heart, but its muscles are still not strong enough. At the age of six, the nerve cells of the cerebral cortex develop, and in terms of weight and appearance, they approach those of adults. Therefore, it is necessary to treat the child's nerves very carefully. It is necessary to ensure that his pronunciation is clear and his speech is fluent. If the child has a defect in this activity, it is necessary to take measures to prevent it. It is necessary to pay special attention to the development of the vocabulary of children of this age. The words in their speech should fully satisfy the child's needs for expression. During this period, children's mathematical thinking and calculation skills should be developed. Basic economic concepts are needed. It is appropriate to pay special attention to the rapid development of the child's imagination.

6. Developmental characteristics of the school preparatory group (6-7 year old children). In the seventh year of a child's life, the range of actions in him expands and becomes more defined, the mutual adjustment of actions in his body begins. 6-7-year-old children begin to be able to manage themselves and control their actions. Boys of this age develop independent activity, initiative, and desire to listen to the opinion of adults. During this period, the height of the child reaches 120 cm, its weight is 22-24 kg. At this age, the child trains, becomes curious, and can control his own health. His power of perception and thinking develop rapidly, he begins to seek to know the material existence. Hygienic skills are formed in children. In the process of preparing a child for school, it is necessary to instill in them a passion for learning, which is a new type of activity. In this place, it is necessary to teach the initial educational elements in order to prepare children to enter the spiritual education process. Any six-year-old child can be admitted to the school. For this, he must be physically, mentally and mentally ready for education. When determining the level of readiness of children for school, it is necessary to rely on the conclusions of diagnostic centers. In addition, the material and technical base of the school must be able to teach six-year-old children. When the teacher's level of pedagogical and psychological knowledge, morals and personal qualities are suitable for teaching and training six-year-old children, he has the right to teach six-year-old children. Therefore, 6-7-year-old children, the schools that receive them, and the teachers who teach these children should be diagnosed separately from the pedagogical and psychological point of view, and only then should they be included in the educational process.

Studying the phenomenon of personal initiative from a socio-psychological point of view, creating a mechanism for its manifestation is currently one of the urgent problems. In the

research aimed at determining the place of tolerance in ensuring the socialization of a person to the society, it was also determined that individual initiative is important when studying tolerance as the basis of the integration process. While thinking about initiative, M. Frese emphasized that the goals of an initiative person are not given or assigned by someone else, but rather, these goals are developed by the person himself. While talking about the qualities of an enterprising person, it is impossible not to talk about leadership and personal motivation, another characteristic that is necessary for society.

Analyzing the existing literature on initiative and leadership, we can see that there are different approaches to studying these phenomena. In some studies, initiative is a characteristic of leadership, and in some studies, on the contrary, leadership is emphasized as a characteristic of an initiative person, and in some studies, initiative and leadership are studied as personality phenomena. Success-oriented individuals have high self-control and management qualities. Those who are afraid of failure prefer a small or, on the contrary, a high level of risk. A person is motivated to achieve success - in order to achieve a goal, his willingness to take risks decreases. At the same time, success motivation also affects success expectations: with strong success motivation, success hope is lower than with weak success motivation. Also, people who are motivated to achieve and have high expectations of success tend to avoid high risk. Those who are highly motivated to succeed and willing to take risks have fewer accidents than those who are highly motivated to take risks but have a high level of motivation to avoid failure (defense).

On the contrary, if a person has a high motivation to avoid failure (defense), this will interfere with the achievement of the goal of success. In addition, T.V. Bendas, the quality of leadership often determines the fate of a group or organization, and the need for a leader almost always arises in situations where the work cannot be done alone.

Conclusion: So, there are many and significant age-related characteristics of the development of children of preschool educational institutions. The child's development, age-appropriate weight, height, psychological character, abilities, the extent to which he receives information from outside, the growth of his point of view, all these things are of great importance. From birth to school age, the child's development should be monitored in all aspects. Because a healthy and enterprising child is the future of our country.

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